

100% Completed

Participant's consent (the Aasis project)

 Mandatory questions are marked with a star (*)

Aasis project 2023-2027 | Academy of Finland | University of Helsinki, University of Jyväskylä, Aalto University

CONSENT OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

I have been asked to participate in the Aasis research project funded by the Academy of Finland. I have received sufficient information about the research and its purpose, the content and use of the material, including the processing and storage of personal data.

By filling this form, I confirm that I have received the [information sheet for research participants](#) and [privacy notice](#).

I understand that participation in this research is voluntary. I have the right to discontinue participation in the research at any time. I am not required to state the reason for the withdrawal and there will be no negative consequences.

Contact information

1. Name *

First name

Surname

2. Contact information

Will not be given outside the research project and will only be used for research-related communication.

Telephone

Email *

Consent

3. My information may be used in the Aasis research. *

- I give permission
 I do not give permission

4. I may be contacted when follow-up on the research is planned (feedback, interviews) *

- I give permission
 I do not give permission

5. My speech samples (audio only) may be used by the project team members for research or educational purposes for teachers and raters (without name / contact information) *

- I give permission
 I do not give permission

6. My speaking performances (video) may be used by the project team members for research or educational purposes for teachers and raters (without name / school / contact information) *

- I give permission
 I do not give permission

7. The research material may be permanently stored in the Language Bank of Finland or similar trusted data archive and it may be used in other research related to language learning (without name, including audio and video recordings) *

- I give permission
 I do not give permission

8. Comments

Submit